

Coupling of p,E and x,t in Special Relativity, Uniform Distribution in x,t and Quantum Mechanics

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In previous notes we argued that free particle quantum mechanics arises from special relativity. We considered two different approaches. The first was using the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ and arguing that a similar expression: $-E \Delta t + p \Delta x = 0$ if $\Delta t = \text{constant}/E$ and $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$. The second approach was to argue that pc and E Lorentz transform as x, ct and so there must exist an equation of the form $x=vt$, namely $1/E = cc/v = 1/p$ which suggests that $\text{constant}/E = \Delta t$ and $\text{constant}/p = \Delta x$. The point that we make is that special relativity seems to link pc, E to x, ct as both transform under the same Lorentz transformation which is essentially a spacetime transformation which enforces $x'=vt'$ for a particle with rest mass at $x=0, t$ in the rest frame. This same transformation applies to photons for which $x/t=c$ and $x'/t'=c$. In Newtonian mechanics, there is no such association between pc, E and x, ct .

In other notes, we argued that the Newtonian spatial probability $P(x)=1/L$ holds for a particle with constant speed. $P(t) = 1/T$ holds also. (Here L is an arbitrary length and T , an arbitrary time.) The point we make is that neither p nor E appear in these expressions, but according to the arguments of the first paragraph, pc, E and x, ct are supposed to be coupled according to special relativity, e.g. $-Et+px$. If they are coupled, how does E and pc as well as x and ct drop out of $P(x)$ and $P(t)$? Given the form $-Et+px$, it is very simple to obtain a function, a power $\{ \text{constant} [-Et+px] \}$ multiplied by a power $\{ -\text{constant} [-Et+px] \}$ such that one obtains 1. One may use Maxwell-Boltzmann type probability arguments to show that $a=e$ and $\text{constant} = 1$. Thus, we argue that it is special relativity which forces one to deal with a coupled expression in p, E, x, t which loses all of these pieces of information in order to create $P(x)=\text{constant}$, $P(t)=\text{constant}$.

In Newtonian mechanics no such issue arises as there is no association of ct with x or (pc, E) with (x, ct) . These ideas in turn lead to the quantum free particle $\exp(-iEt+px)$.

Newtonian Mechanics

In Newtonian mechanics, a particle with constant speed in the x direction has:

$P(x) = 1/L$ and $P(t) = 1/T$, where L is an arbitrary length and T , an arbitrary time interval ((1))

Here the two probabilities are decoupled and x and t are not part of a 4-vector. Furthermore, p (momentum) and E , energy are completely decoupled from this problem. As a result, one leaves ((1)) as it is and there is no issue.

Special Relativity

((1)) holds in special relativity in any particular frame for a particle moving with constant speed. There are two issues, however, that now come into play:

- (A) X and ct are part of a 4-vector and should not be considered separately, but ((1)) still has $P(x)=1/L$ and $P(t) = 1/T$ as independent statements
- (B) P and E are no longer decoupled from x and t . They also form a 4-vector and transform according to the spacetime Lorentz transformation. This coupling is exemplified by $-Et+px$.

We have argued before that one may derive the Lorentz transformation as a spacetime transformation (i.e. applying to (x,ct) by considering a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t and insisting that $x'=vt'$. This leads to a matrix with a parameter b which has units of velocity and holds in all frames. Given that this transformation applies to spacetime, x,ct , it should also hold for a photon which is part of the same spacetime. A photon, however, does not have a rest mass or rest frame and so $x/t=c$ and $x'/t'=c$ must hold. The same transformation (Lorentz) then applies to both a particle with rest mass m_0 and a photon if $b=c$. We have further argued that this transformation applies to (pc, E) . This is a key idea because now p,E and x,t are coupled in a sense because they both transform according to the Lorentz spacetime transformation. This may be quantified by the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et+px = \text{constant} \quad ((2))$$

Thus, one has the Newtonian $P(x)=1/L$ and $P(t) = 1/T$ as well as the coupled expression ((2)). ((2)) applies to densities because it applies to sample points in x and t . For example, a set of sample points x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3 all at t in one frame become:

$$x_i' = g(v) x_i + gvt \quad \text{and} \quad t_i' = gv x_i + gt \quad \text{where} \quad g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((3))$$

We argue that special relativity forces one to map a function of ((2)) into the two functions $P(x)=1/L$ and $P(t) = 1/T$. ((4))

Given that E,p, x,t all disappear in ((4)), one may use:

$$A \text{ power } \{\text{constant } [-Et+px]\} * A \text{ power } \{\text{constant } [-Et+px]\} \quad ((5))$$

A product is required to remove $-Et+px$ which suggests that each term:

$$A \text{ power } \{\text{constant } [-Et+px]\} \quad ((6)) \quad \text{or with } -\text{constant}$$

may have some meaning because $-Et+px$ has meaning.

To find A and constant, one may consider ((6)) as also playing the role of a kind of probability and arguing that

$$\text{Ln} [((6))] = \text{information} = -Et+px \quad ((7))$$

((7)) yields $A=e$, but means ((6)) is a growing or falling function with x,t so ((7)) should have an i inserted as a factor of $-Et+px$ to make the function periodic.

Thus, one obtains $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ by trying to make $P(x)=1/L$ and $P(t)=1/T$ compatible with $-Et+px$ from special relativity. This, we argue, leads to free particle quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that in Newtonian mechanics one has $P(x)=1/L$ and $P(t) = 1/T$ for a particle with constant speed. There is no issue here at all as x and t are not part of a 4-vector and decoupled from E and p which depend on m_0 and v . Such is not the case in special relativity. First of all, (x,ct) form a 4-vector and secondly (pc,E) also form a 4-vector. p,E and x,t are coupled through the Lorentz invariant: $-Et+px = \text{constant}$. This coupled form in special relativity must somehow allow for E,p,t,x to disappear so to speak and also decouple to yield $P(x)=1/L$ and $P(t)=1/T$. We suggest that there must exist two functions $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and $\exp(iEt-ipx)$ such that when multiplied together yield a constant, but the $\exp(-iEt)$, $\exp(iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ also yield a constant when multiplied separately. Thus, making $P(x)=1/L$ and $P(t)=1/T$ compatible with the p,E coupled with x,t : $-Et+px$ leads to the quantum free particle wavefunction: $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.